

The Role of Workplace Fun in Enhancing Organizational Outcomes a Study on Sadat City University

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Abstract

This paper attempts to determine the role of Workplace Fun (WF) in enhancing Organizational Outcomes (OO) at Sadat City University (SCU). Using Tews et al., 2014 for measuring WF and Shamsuddin & Abdul Rahman, 2014; Demir, 2014; Imam, et al., 2014; Albdour, et al., 2014; Davoudi & Allahyari, 2013; Cicei, 2012; Luthans, 2011; Bauer & Erdogan, 2010; Pugno & Depedri, 2009; Yen, 2008; Jacqueline & Kessler, 2004 for measuring OO. The study develops a number of hypotheses and tests them. Of the 400 questionnaires that were distributed, 300 usable questionnaires were returned, a response rate of 75%.

The research has reached a number of results, the most important of which are: (1) the responses of faculty members at SCU showed that there is a low tendency towards the leadership in the university towards the practice of FA and their support for fun. This indicates that most leaders follow the standards, policies and regulatory procedures from the point of view of the teaching process, (2) the university faculties are aware of the OO in the work through the university's interest in the excellence of its leaders and their brilliance in their work, services, innovations and leadership support for the values, considerations and customs of the university. In addition, the investment of implicit and explicit knowledge in their work, and (3) research has shown that WF has an effective role in increasing the event of fun and fun atmosphere for employees characterized by recreational activities and competitions to change their psychological well-being.

The research concluded that: (1) the management should encourage employees to socialize with each other and emphasize the joke and the importance of humor. Human resource managers must enhance pleasure in the workplace through formal and informal methods, (2) the University of Sadat City and its faculties take into consideration that achieving OO. This can not be achieved unless high standards of excellence are achieved at the university and individual levels focusing on unique organizational resources and capabilities in order to achieve their organizational objectives, (3) fun work environment should be provided at SCU and its faculties. This can be done by supporting the social and psychological activities of the employees. This will enhance their attitudes towards the university and enhance personal relations. This will improve the OO, (4) leaders at SCU and its faculties must have a moral duty to create an organizational culture that encourages creativity, respect for laws, and personal initiative that is consistent with the mission and goals of the university, and (5) the current stage at SCU under the competition and obtaining local and international rankings on the quality of education and academic accreditation requires the creation of new knowledge and innovations that contribute to the achievement of OO. In addition, their brilliance in the leadership of thought and organizational intelligence builds the educational system that maintains learning and innovation commensurate with the provision of services to the community.

1. Introduction

An enjoyable work environment and a range of enjoyable activities positively affect the position and productivity of individuals and groups and increase their well-being and interaction among employees (Choi et al., 2015).

In a lifetime, an average person will spend more than 90,000 hours on the job- too much time not to have WF. Successfully integrating WF requires a leader setting the vision and tone for the journey (Everett, 2011).

Workplace Fun (WF) is mainly related to three key aspects: the "fun climate" - the climate in which the elements are fun in the organization, the second aspect - "the fun of the individual" - the individual style of fun and excitement, and finally the "fun of the workplace" leisure activities, entertainment, social and personal activities, and humor (In & Ching, 2010).

WF is an activity that guides fun and increases institutional performance and encourages employees towards creativity and job satisfaction (Bolton & Houlihon, 2009).

WF is engaging in fun activities and entertainment that increases the psyche of workers (McDowell, 2005).

There are three aspects of WF. They are (1) the fun climate is management that means promoting fun elements, (2) the fun person is fun at the individual level. (3) fun, entertaining and fun activities that support WF (McDowell, 2004).

There are two types of WF. They are a tangible and intangible pleasure. WF had real fun activities, for example, video games, sports (Meyer, 1999), meals and games (Karl et al., 2005), the feelings or climate in the organization (Broussine et al., 1999).

2. Workplace Fun

Social events, celebrations, and entertainment add much to WF (Grant et al., 2014).

Employees' satisfaction, commitment, and productivity are higher with WF and vice versa (Tews et al., 2012).

WF, in general, is perceived as a positive subjective experience (Baldry & Hallier 2010).

WF is an expression of the authentic self and associated it with diversity (Fleming & Sturdy, 2009).

WF typically gains its spontaneity, surprise, and often subversion of the extant order (Fineman, 2006). WF is designed to fun activities that are expected to improve OO (Choi et al., 2013).

WF is spontaneous, contextual and has an unmanaged, liberated element that defies control (Plester, 2009).

WF has positive consequences on employees. WF has far-reaching effects on employees and organizations (Owler et al., 2010).

WF is a playful social, interpersonal, recreational, or task activities intended to provide amusement, enjoyment, or pleasure (Lamm & Meeks, 2009).

WF is fun drawing an implicit link between, play, fun, laughter and increasing corporate performance, in the forms of motivation, creativity and job satisfaction (Bolton & Houlihon, 2009).

WF is any social, interpersonal, or task activities at work of a playful or humorous nature which provides an individual with amusement, enjoyment or pleasure. It includes construct dimensions, process mechanisms, and performance outcomes, and building. It is social, personal, or important activities in the work of fun or comic nature that provides an individual with fun (Fluegge, 2008).

WF affects additional role behaviors. Fun enhances mission motivation by providing energy to employees. This means that when managers encourage fun, they increase energy towards difficult tasks (Fluegge, 2008).

WF is engaging in activities not specifically related to the job that is enjoyable, amusing or playful (McDowell, 2005).

WF is a playful, social, interpersonal, recreational, or task activities intended to provide amusement, enjoyment, or pleasure (Chan, 2010; Karl et al., 2005).

WF is engaging in activities not specifically related to the job that is enjoyable, amusing, or playful (McDowell, 2004).

WF is a work environment that intentionally encourages, initiates, and supports a variety of enjoyable and pleasurable activities, such as participating in parties, giving awards, playing competitions, and gathering to have fun activities (Ford et al., 2003).

WF plays an important role in influencing the organization's output. There is three dimensions of WF. They are FA, CS, and MS (Muceldili & Erdila, 2016; Tews et al., 2012; 2014). These dimensions are illustrated as follows:

1. **Fun Activities (FA):** It refers to the official activities undertaken by the organization such as competitions, and building the activities of the team. Leisure activities play an important role in the communication of individuals and promote friendly communication and intimate friendship among individuals. FA is an essential part of the organization's activities. Leisure activities in the workplace are an effective way to create an enjoyable working environment, where workers see it as more fun to create an effective performance.
2. **Coworker Socialization (CS):** It consists of informal activities by co-workers, such as going out together or joking with each other. Many of the Organization's old staff members meet newly recruited individuals and their socialization in the Organization, requiring everyone in the Organization to have a friendly and intimate relationship. Everyone who comes along with others increases the fun process. Regular interaction of individuals with each other increases their well-being towards work.

3. **Manager Support (MS):** It is the support required by the manager for all formal and informal activities such as encouraging fun allowing official competitions, friendly gatherings, and social clubs. The director's support for the fun of all recreational activities has a strong impact on individual productivity and performance.

3. Organizational Outcomes

Organizational outcomes are the purpose that the organization seeks, or the results it seeks to achieve in the work environment. To achieve this, organizations are concerned with positive behaviors and behaviors that increase organizational outcomes and avoid negative behaviors that reduce those outcomes (Walker, 2000).

Organizational outputs are a set of behavioral and situational outputs that the organization wishes to reach in order to achieve organizational success and thus achieve its long-term goals. Organizational outcomes include Organizational Commitment (OC), Job Performance (JP), and Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). In addition, the organizations are working to reduce the negative behaviors within the organization (absenteeism, lack of responsibility and low efficiency of employees). There are many internal and external factors that affect organizational outcomes. Internal factors are turnover, high absenteeism, intention to quit, and external factors, such as competition, technology, and management. Successful organizations must, therefore, use and nurture individual efforts of employees to overcome these factors (Grawitch & Barber, 2009).

There is three dimensions of OO. These are: JP, OCB, and OC (Shamsuddin & Abdul Rahman, 2014; Demir, 2014; Imam, et al., 2014; Albdour, et al., 2014; Davoudi & Allahyari, 2013; Cicei, 2012; Luthans, 2011; Bauer & Erdogan, 2010; Pugno & Depedri, 2009; Yen, 2008; Jacqueline & Kessler, 2004). These dimensions are illustrated as follows:

3.1. Job Performance

JP is one of the important areas of research and organizational practice, as it represents the key role in all employees' decisions, such as efficiency compensation and the ability to retain employees (Shamsuddin & Abdul Rahman, 2014).

JP is an important issue for the organization and indicates whether the employee is doing well or not. JP consists of the behaviors of employees in their jobs that are related to the achievement of the organization's goals. The arrangement work in the organization has a significant positive impact on JP (Davoudi & Allahyari, 2013).

JP is the performance level of factors listed in the job description card. It varies from work to job. JP includes the quality and quantity of work done by the worker, the accuracy and speed with which the work is performed, the effectiveness of the person doing the work, and the rewards he receives for additional work. JP is one of the most important organizational outcomes studied in organizational behavior (Bauer & Erdogan, 2010).

Incentives play an important role in the lives of employees. Some organizations use motivation as a tool to achieve job satisfaction, which has an impact on their performance. There is a strong correlation between JP and job satisfaction (Pugno & Depedri, 2009).

3.2. Organizational Citizenship Behavior

OCB is the collaborative effort of the staff in the organization. It is a set of innovative cooperative behaviors (Organ, 1977).

OCB is individual behavior that does not fall within the requirements of formal work and at the same time is an important tool for the development of organizational performance (Jacqueline & Kessler, 2004).

OCB is the activity of the individual to perform work indirectly in the work environment. It includes helping coworkers, adhering to the rules and regulations of the work environment, and effective participation in the decision-making process, as well as bearing the working conditions without any complaint from work (Yen, 2008).

OCB is a set of job-related behaviors that is not recognized by organizational reward systems and seeks to enhance the effective functioning of the organization (Cicei, 2012).

OCB consists of functional behaviors that require contributing to the overall success of the organization as an exceptional role that positively affects the efficiency and effectiveness of the organization's performance (Demir, 2014).

The dimensions of OCB are (1) to be voluntary, not in the job description card, (2) to be behavior directed by the organization, and (3) to be of a multidimensional nature (Demir, 2014).

3.3. Organizational Commitment

OC is of great importance in the life of organizations. Management in any organization is concerned about the OC of employees. The commitment of employees towards the organization is of great importance and directly affects the performance of employees in the organization. OC plays an important role in forecasting goals and objectives, improving productivity, and reducing absenteeism and turnover in any organization (Imam, et al., 2014).

There is considerable interest among researchers in the study of OC. This is demonstrated by the numerous studies carried out in this field. OC leads to positive behavior within the organization by employees such as high performance, OCB, and other positive behaviors that must be in the organization (Albdour, et al., 2014).

There are a range of different concepts of OC: (1) the strong desire of the worker to remain a member within a particular organization, (2) willingness to exert high levels of effort on behalf of the organization; and (3) a clear belief in accepting the understanding of the values and culture of the organization (Luthans, 2011).

4. Research Model

The research framework suggests that WF (independent variable) has an impact on OO (dependent variable) at SCU.

WF is measured in terms of FA, CS, and MS at SCU (Tews et al., 2014). Also, OO is measured in terms of JP, OCB and OC (Shamsuddin & Abdul Rahman, 2014; Demir, 2014; Imam, et al., 2014; Albdour, et al., 2014; Davoudi & Allahyari, 2013; Cicei, 2012; Luthans, 2011; Bauer & Erdogan, 2010; Pugno & Depedri, 2009; Yen, 2008; Jacqueline & Kessler, 2004).

Figure (1)
The Research Model

5. Research Questions

The researcher reached to the research problem through two sources. The first is the previous studies that dealt with the relationship between WF and OO. This called for the researcher to test this relationship in the Egyptian environment in general and SCU in particular.

In light of the review of previous studies towards WF, literature indicated a gap in the literature that showed the relationship between fun and experimental participation. The study has investigated the relationship between fun and participation through qualitative data (Plester, 2016).

WF (FA, CS, and MS) can have a normative effect on responsibility and participation (Tew et al., 2014).

WF activities are negatively related to turnover. Manager supports for fun negatively related to turnover. The impact of FA on turnover is stronger when there are greater levels of MS. The impact of FA on performance is stronger when there are greater levels of MS (Tews et al., 2013).

WF involves designed FA that is expected to improve organizational outcomes (Choi et al., 2013). Fun can be a powerful tool for promoting engagement in organizations, leading to emotions, knowledge, and behaviors. The creation of an agile and active regulatory context helps facilitate participation in employment (Bakker et al., 2011).

WF is positively associated with participation and contracting in white-collar workers that supports previous studies. When employees look at MS, they will be motivated by constructive changes in their workplace (Owler, 2010). WF has a positive effect on employee engagement in organizations (Plester, 2009).

WF was positively related to job satisfaction and negatively related to turnover intentions (Karl et al., 2008). Fun was positively related to work engagement, positive affect, task performance, creative performance, and OCB (Fluegge, 2008). There is a positive relationship between WF and job satisfaction (Karl et al., 2007). There is a positive relationship between experiencing fun and job satisfaction (Karl & Peluchette, 2006). Fun was positively related to job satisfaction and negatively related to emotional exhaustion (Karl & Peluchette, 2006). WF supports a variety of enjoyable and pleasurable activities that positively impact the attitude and productivity of individuals and groups (Ford et al., 2003). Fun is an important part of organizational life. We can increase morale and productivity and decrease burnout and turnover by interjecting more fun and playfulness into work routines such as safety activities (Geller, 2003).

WF has gained attention through a growing interest in the positive psychology movement. Positive organizational studies and positive organizational behavior increases the pleasure of recreation in the workplace (Cameron et al., 2003). Moreover, there is some empirical evidence showed the positive relationship between WF and employees' job satisfaction (Lundin et al., 2002). The second source to determine the research problem is the pilot study which was conducted at SCU. The researcher found several indicators explain the importance of WF in affecting OO at SCU. The research questions are as follows:

Q1: What is the relationship between WF (Fun Activities) and OO at Sadat City University?

Q2: What is the nature of the relationship between WF (Coworker Socializing) and OO at Sadat City University?

Q3: What is the extent of the relationship between WF (Manager Support for Fun) and OO at Sadat City University?

6. Research Hypotheses

In light of the previous WF studies, the literature highlighted the direct impact of WF on workplace participation (Plester & Hutchison, 2016). WF activities are positively related to performance. Manager supports for fun positively related to performance. The impact of FA and MS on turnover is mediated by affective commitment. The impact of FA and MS on performance is mediated by affective commitment (Tews et al., 2013). There are a number of business researchers maintain that WF is essential for enhancing employee motivation and productivity while reducing stress (Choi et al., 2013).

Managers influence the views of employees in their work when managers confirm the WF. Employees tend to show higher participation in their jobs and willing to invest themselves in their work (Christian et al., 2011). Management scientists tend to investigate WF to enhance staff engagement and empowerment recently (Bolton & Holihan, 2009).

WF leads to increasing enthusiasm of employees, organizational cohesiveness and satisfaction of employees (O'Brien & Allen, 2008).

Fun was positively related to job satisfaction, as well as negatively related to emotional exhaustion and emotional dissonance (Karl et al., 2007).

WF was positively related to job satisfaction and employees’ perceptions of customer service quality (Karl & Peluchette, 2006). WF is positively related to job satisfaction and affective OC and negatively related to turnover intentions (McDowell, 2005). Another study suggested that an environment is considered fun when it intentionally encourages, initiates, and supports a variety of enjoyable and pleasurable activities that positively impact the attitude and productivity of individuals and groups (Ford et al., 2003).

WF leads to the increasing motivation of employees, productivity, and enhancing customer satisfaction (Lundin et al., 2002; McGhee, 2000; Paulson, 2001; Ramsey, 2001; Weiss, 2002). A fun working environment is much more productive than a routine environment (Von-Oech, 1982).The following hypotheses were developed to decide if there is a significant correlation between WF and OO.

H1: There is no relationship between WF (Fun Activities) and OO at Sadat City University

H2: WF (Co-worker Socializing) has no significant effect on OO t Sadat City University in Egypt.

H3: There is no relationship between WF (Manager Support for Fun) and OO at Sadat City University

7. Research Population

The total population at SCU in Egypt is 801 employees. Due to the small number of members of the research community, it was decided to study this community using comprehensive inventory (Complete Numeration or Census) to get the highest percentage of survey lists. The research population is illustrated in the following table:

Table (1) Distribution of the Sample Size

Faculty Members	Number	Percentage
1. Faculty of Veterinary Medicine	154	19%
2. Faculty of Tourism & Hotels	93	12%
3. Genetic Engineering Research Institute	124	16%
4. Faculty of Physical Education	186	23%
5. Faculty of Education	49	6%
6. Faculty of Commerce	69	9%
7. Faculty of Law	59	7%
8. Institute for Environmental Studies and Research	50	6%
9. Faculty of Pharmacy	17	2%
Total	801	100%

Source: Staff Members Affairs Department, Sadat University, Egypt, 2018

Table (2) provides a respondent profile of the sample at Sadat City University in Egypt.

8. The Survey Structure

The survey used to measure WF and OO at SCU. This survey consists of three parts. The first described the objectives of the research by asking the respondents to participate in the survey. The second asked for the respondents’ demographic variable such as gender, academic degree, marital status, age, and period of experience. The third presented the questions related to WF and OO at SCU.

About 400 questionnaires were distributed. 300 usable questionnaires. The response rate was 75%.

The research depends on the Likert scale for each statement ranging from (5) “full agreement,” (4) for “agree,” (3) for “neutral,” (2) for “disagree,” and (1) for “full disagreement.”

Table (2) Characteristics of sample unit

Demographic Variables		Number	Percentage
1- Gender	Male	156	52%
	Female	144	48%
	Total	300	100%
2- The Academic Degree	Professor degree	51	17%
	Associate professor	72	24%
	Assistant professor	96	32%
	Lecturer	30	10%
	Demonstrator	51	17%
	Total	300	100%
3- Marital Status	Married	225	75%
	Single	75	25%
	Total	300	100%
4- Age	Less than 30 years	45	15%
	From 30 to 45	135	45%
	More than 45	120	40%
	Total	300	100%
5- Period of Experience	Less than 5 years	144	48%
	From 5 to 10	99	33%
	More than 10	57	19%
	Total	300	100%

SPSS, V.23, 2015

9. Data Analysis and Hypotheses Testing

9.1. Coding of variables

The main variables, sub-variables, and methods of measuring variables can be explained in the following table:

Table (3)
Description and Measuring of the Research Variables

Main Variables		Sub-Variables	Number of Statement	Methods of Measuring Variables
Independent Variable	WF	FA	5	Tews et al., 2014
		CS	4	
		MS	5	
		Total Measurement	14	
Dependent Variable	OO	JP	6	Shamsuddin & Abdul Rahman, 2014; Demir, 2014; Imam, et al., 2014; Albdour, et al., 2014; Davoudi & Allahyari, 2013; Cicei, 2012; Luthans, 2011; Bauer & Erdogan, 2010; Pugno & Depedri, 2009; Yen, 2008; Jacqueline & Kessler, 2004.
		OCB	7	
		OC	8	
		Total Measurement	21	

9.2. Construct Validity

The researcher depends on the method of Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) in order to verify the quality of the various research measures. CFA was applied to the research variables as follows:

9.2.1. Workplace Fun

The researcher used CFA for WF. This variable consists of three dimensions. They are FA, CS, and MS. The total number of WF is 14 statement. This can be illustrated by the following figure:

Figure (2)
CFA For WF

Source: AMOS, V.23, 2015

From the previous figure, it is clear that all the statement of WF is greater than 0.50, which corresponds to GFI. This is a good indicator of all other statistical analysis. The researcher depends on the Structural Equation Model (SEM) because it is the best ways to test the compatibility model using AMOS analysis. The quality indicators for WF can be illustrated in the following table:

Table (4)
Quality Indicators for WF Using AMOS Analysis

Test the Quality of the Model Acceptance Condition ^(*)	Test Value
$X^2 / \text{Degree of freedom} < 5$	1347.261
P. value > 0.5	0.000
Goodness of fit Index (GFI) > 0.90	0.564
Tuker-Lewis Index (TLI) > 0.95	0.584
Comparative Fit Index (CFI) > 0.95	0.662
Normed Fit Index (NFI) > 0.90	0.650
Incremental Fit Index (IFI) > 0.95	0.663

^(*) Daire et al., 2008

Source: AMOS, V.23, 2015

In light of the above-mentioned indicators, it is clear that the previous indicators are good for making all other statistical analysis.

9.2.2. Organizational Outcomes

The researcher used CFA for OO which consists of three dimensions. They are JP, OCB, and OC. The total number of WF is 21 statement. This can be illustrated in Figure (2).

Figure (3)
CFA For OO

Source: AMOS, V.23, 2015

According to Figure (2), it is clear that all the statement of OO is greater than 0.50, which corresponds to GFI. This is a good indicator of all other statistical analysis. The researcher depends on the SEM because it is the best ways to test the compatibility model using AMOS analysis. The quality indicators for OO can be illustrated in the following table:

Table (5)
Quality Indicators for OO Using AMOS Analysis

Test the Quality of the Model Acceptance Condition ^(*)	Test Value
X ² / Degree of freedom < 5	2164.580
P. value > 0.5	0.000
Goodness of fit Index (GFI) > 0.90	0.593
Tuker-Lewis Index (TLI) > 0.95	0.621
Comparative Fit Index (CFI) > 0.95	0.665
Normed Fit Index (NFI) > 0.90	0.646
Incremental Fit Index (IFI) > 0.95	0.666

(*) Daire et al., 2008

Source: AMOS, V.23, 2015

In light of the above-mentioned indicators, it is clear that the previous indicators are good for making all other statistical analysis.

9.3. Descriptive Analysis

Table (6): shows the mean and standard deviations of WF and OO

Variables	The Dimension	Mean	Standard Deviation
WF	FA	3.68	1.030
	CS	3.93	0.702
	MS	3.71	1.190
	Total Measurement	3.76	0.761
OO	JP	3.44	0.852
	OCB	4.12	0.768
	OC	4.10	0.846
	Total Measurement	3.91	0.564

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

According to Table (6), among the various facets of WF, most of the respondents identified the presence of FA ($M=3.68$, $SD=1.030$), CS ($M=3.93$, $SD=0.702$), MS ($M=3.71$, $SD=1.190$), and total WF ($M=3.76$, $SD=0.761$).

The second issue examined was the different facets of OO. Most of the respondents identified the presence of JP ($M=3.44$, $SD=0.852$), OCB ($M=4.12$, $SD=0.768$), OC ($M=4.10$, $SD=0.846$), and total OO ($M=3.91$, $SD=0.564$).

9.4. Evaluating Reliability

Table (7): Reliability of WF and OO

Variables	Dimension	Number of Statement	ACC
WF	FA	5	0.877
	CS	4	0.794
	MS	5	0.909
	Total Measurement	14	0.879
OO	JP	6	0.851
	OCB	7	0.862
	OC	8	0.890
	Total Measurement	21	0.861

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

Table (7) presents the reliability of WF and OO. WF is reliable because ACC is 0.879. ACC for FA is 0.877. ACC for CS is 0.794 while ACC for MS is 0.909. Thus, the internal consistency of WF can be acceptable.

Also, OO is reliable because the ACC is 0.861. ACC for JP is 0.851. ACC for OCB is 0.862 while ACC for OC is 0.890. Thus, the internal consistency of OO can be acceptable.

Finally, there are two scales were defined, WF (14 variables), where ACC represented about 0.879, and OO (21 variables), where ACC represented 0.861.

9.5. The Means, St. Deviations, and Correlation among Variables

Table (8): Means, Standard Deviations and Intercorrelations among Variables

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	WF	OO
WF	3.76	0.761	1	
OO	3.91	0.564	0.535**	1

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

Regarding Table (8), the level of WF is high (Mean=3.76; SD=0.761), while OO is (Mean=3.91; SD=0.564). The overall correlation between WF and OO is 0.535.

9.6. The Correlation between WF and OO

Table (9): Correlation Matrix between WF and OO

Research Variables	1	2	3	4
Fun Activities	1			
Coworker Socializing	0.415**	1		
Manager Support for Fun	0.408**	0.176	1	
OO	0.475**	0.346**	0.381**	1

Note: ** Correlation is significant at 0.01 level

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

Based on the Table (9), the correlation between WF (FA) and OO is 0.475. For WF (CS) and OO, the value is 0.346 whereas WF (MS) and OO show correlation value of 0.381.

9.7. Workplace Fun (FA) and OO

The relationship between WF (FA) and OO is determined. The first hypothesis to be tested is:

H1: There is no relationship between WF (Fun Activities) and OO at Sadat City University.

As Table (10) proves that there is a relationship between WF (FA), it represents 48%, according to MCC. Also, WF (FA) may interpret about 23% according to DC. Therefore, it was decided to refuse the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant statistical impact of WF (FA) on OO. The alternative hypothesis has been accepted because MRA had shown that there was a relationship at a statistical significance level of 0.01 (according to F-Test) between WF (FA) and OO according to T-test (See table 10).

Table (10): MRA Results for WF (FA) and OO

The Variables of WF (FA)	Beta	R	R ²
1. My faculty is interested in public celebrations and achievements in work.	0.201*	0.432	0.186
2. My faculty is interested in building the activities of the various entertainment teams.	0.141	0.417	0.173
3. My faculty is interested in recognizing personal characteristics.	0.127	0.341	0.116
4. My faculty is interested in social events and events.	0.038	0.365	0.133
5. My faculty is interested in holding various entertainment competitions.	0.072	0.383	0.146
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F 		0.480 0.231 17.648 5, 294 3.01	
** P < .01 * P < .05			

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

9.8. Workplace Fun (CS) and OO

The relationship between WF (CS) and OO is determined. The second hypothesis to be tested is:

H2: WF (Co-worker Socializing) has no significant effect on OO at Sadat City University in Egypt.

Table (11) MRA Results for WF (CS) and OO

The Variables of WF (CS)	Beta	R	R ²
1. I share most of my colleagues talking about work at the faculty.	0.254**	0.316	0.099
2. Joking with most of my faculty colleagues.	0.144*	0.259	0.067
3. Mingle with most of my colleagues inside the faculty.	0.288**	0.336	0.112
4. I mingle with most of my faculty colleagues outside of work.	0.236**	0.174	0.030
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F 		0.416 0.173 15. 456 4, 295 3.31	
** P < .01 * P < .05			

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

As Table (11) proves that there is a relationship between WF (CS), it represents 42%, according to MCC. Also, WF (CS) may interpret about 17% according to DC. Therefore, it was decided to refuse the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis because MRA had shown that there was a relationship at a statistical significance level of 0.01 (according to F-Test) between WF (CS) and OO according to T-test (See table 11).

9.9. Workplace Fun (MS) and OO

The relationship between WF (MS) and OO is determined. The third hypothesis to be tested is:

H3: There is no relationship between WF (Manager Support for Fun) and OO at Sadat City University

Table (12): MRA Results for WF (MS) and OO

The Variables of WF MS	Beta	R	R ²
1. Ahead at work encourages employees to do their job.	0.213*	0.316	0.099
2. The head of the work emphasizes the fun in the workplace.	0.057	0.296	0.087
3. Head at work is trying to make the work more fun.	0.094	0.322	0.103
4. Head at work Interested in making fun in the workplace.	0.107	0.350	0.122
5. Head at work allows fun inside the workplace.	0.311**	0.381	0.145
▪ MCC		0.420	
▪ DC		0.176	
▪ Calculated F		12.595	
▪ Degree of Freedom		5, 294	
▪ Indexed F		3.01	
** P < .01	* P < .05		

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

As Table (12) proves that there is a relationship between WF (MS), it represents 42%, according to MCC. Also, WF (MS) may interpret about 17% according to DC. Therefore, it was decided to refuse the null hypothesis which states that there is no impact of WF (MS) on OO. The alternative hypothesis has been accepted because MRA had shown that there was a relationship at a statistical significance level of 0.01 (according to F-Test) between WF (MS). and OO according to T-test (See table 12).

10. Research Results

1. The responses of faculty members at SCU showed that there is a low tendency towards the leadership in the university towards the practice of FA and their support for fun. This indicates that most leaders follow the standards, policies and regulatory procedures from the point of view of the teaching process.
2. The university faculties are aware of OO through the university's interest in the excellence of its leaders and their brilliance in their work, services, innovations and leadership support for the values, considerations, and customs of the university in addition to the investment of implicit and explicit knowledge in their work.
3. Research has shown that WF has an effective role to increase in the event of fun and fun atmosphere for employees characterized by recreational activities and competitions to change their psychological well-being.
4. The researcher used the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) in order to verify the quality of the various research measures. It is clear that all the statement of WF and OO are greater than 0.50, which corresponds to the GFI. This is a good indicator of all other statistical analysis. In addition to that, the researcher depends on SEM because it is one of the best ways to use the multivariable test. SEM has been used to test the compatibility model using AMOS analysis. In order to ascertain whether the model is compatible with the sample data used. Also, it already measures the variable that should be measured. In general, it is clear that the previous indicators are good for making all other statistical analysis.
5. There is a statistically significant relationship between WF (FA, CS, and MS) and OO (JP, OCB, and OC) at SCU, where the greater the interest and the use of WF the greater the ability to enhancing OO at SCU.

11. Recommendations

1. The management should encourage employees to socialize each other and emphasize joking and humor importance. Human resource managers should promote fun in the workplace via formal (public celebrations, social events, competitions) and informal ways (socializing coffee break, joking each other's).
2. The University of Sadat City and its faculties take into consideration that achieving OO. This can not be achieved unless high standards of excellence are achieved at the university and individual levels and focus on unique organizational resources and capabilities in order to achieve their organizational objectives.

3. An enjoyable and fun work environment should be provided at SCU and its faculties. This can be done by supporting the social and psychological activities of the employees. This will enhance their attitudes towards the university and enhance personal relations. This will improve the OO.
4. Leaders at SCU and its faculties must have a moral duty to create an organizational culture that encourages creativity, respect for laws, and personal initiative that is consistent with the mission and goals of the university.
5. The current stage at SCU under the competition and obtaining local and international rankings on the quality of education and academic accreditation requires the creation of new knowledge and innovations that contribute to the achievement of OO. In addition, their brilliance in the leadership of thought and organizational intelligence to build the educational system that maintains learning and innovation commensurate with the provision of services to the community.

12. Conclusion

WF is positively related to organizational excellence. In other words, this study shows that there is a significant statistical relationship between the dimensions of WF and OO at SCU.

Employees with MS are motivated about constructive changes in their workplaces.

Thus the positive side of WF is revealed. The results indicated that MS and CS positively influence taking charge.

WF is not an issue to take lightheartedly in the workplace context, where demands are increasing, and the need for coping strategies to reduce stress is great. Fun could play the role of an important coping mechanism that ameliorates the stressors or demands and contributes to well-being.

13. Limitations and Future Research

There are some limitations to this study. Firstly, the data was collected from employees at SCU in Egypt. Therefore, the generalization of the results must be made with caution. Secondly, the findings may not be generalized to other universities in Egypt. Thirdly, small sample size is used.

There are several areas for future research. They are (1) organizational culture as a moderator variable between WF and job satisfaction, and (2) measuring the reaction of customers to employees who are experiencing fun.

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